

CADRE (Coordinated Access for Data, Research and Environments)

ARDC PLATFORMS PROJECT FINAL REPORT

Ryan Perry
13/12/2024

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1. PROJECT INFORMATION

PROJECT TITLE AND CODE	CADRE (Coordinated Access for Data, Research and Environments)
PROJECT START AND END DATES	May 2021 – Dec 2024
LEAD CONTRACTING ORGANISATION	The Australian National University
SUBCONTRACTOR REPRESENTATIVE	
PROJECT LEAD CONTACT PERSON	Ryan Perry
PROJECT MANAGER	
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	The Australian Access Federation (AAF), Melbourne Institute Data Lab (MIDL), Australian Academic Research Network (AARNet), Research Graph Foundation (RGF), Australian Urban Research Infrastructure Network (AURIN), Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW), Australian Institute of Family Studies (AIFS), University of Melbourne, Melbourne School of Graduate Education (UMELB), Swinburne University, Social Data Analytics Lab (SWIN), UNSW, Centre for Big Data Research in Health (UNSW)
FOCUS AREA and ACTIVITY	

1.1 Background

The CADRE project was undertaken to address critical gaps in data access and governance within the Australian research sector. As the amount of sensitive data held by government, research, and private sector entities has grown, so too have concerns about privacy, data misuse, and the complexity of sharing data responsibly. Although sensitive data is highly valuable for research, especially in the social sciences and related disciplines, the lack of a standardised approach to data access management has presented challenges in making such data accessible for research without compromising privacy or public trust. This need for a reliable and transparent framework drove the development of CADRE, a web-based platform designed to standardise data access requests and support custodians in making well-informed decisions about sensitive data sharing.

Central to CADRE's approach is the operationalisation of the Five Safes framework (see <https://www2.uwe.ac.uk/faculties/BBS/Documents/1601.pdf>), an internationally recognised model that ensures data access decisions are grounded in principles of safety and accountability. Originating from the United Kingdom's Office of National Statistics, the Five Safes has become a best-practice model for managing access to sensitive data in both public and private sectors. The framework considers data safety across five dimensions—Safe People, Safe Projects, Safe Settings, Safe Data, and Safe Outputs—ensuring that data sharing decisions are made with a thorough understanding of the associated risks across these dimensions. Adopting this model within CADRE enables Australian research institutions and data custodians to apply a consistent, principles-based approach to evaluating data requests.

CADRE was developed in collaboration with research institutions, government agencies, and other partners, each of whom brought unique insights and requirements to the project. Throughout the development process, it became clear that existing methods for managing sensitive data access—such as traditional data de-identification or ad hoc sharing agreements—were unsuited to the increasing complexities and frequency of data sharing. Advances in computational methods and the proliferation of data sources that could potentially reveal identifiable information underscore the need for more secure, standardised access methods.

CADRE addresses the practical challenges faced by data custodians in managing access requests. By providing a unified dashboard, CADRE allows custodians to streamline the process of receiving, reviewing, and approving data access requests, while simultaneously recording and tracking data sharing agreements. This approach not only saves time but also provides a transparent, auditable record of data sharing activities, helping custodians maintain compliance with evolving data governance regulations and frameworks, including the 2022 Data Availability and Transparency Bill.

Developed through partnerships with universities, government agencies, and other research infrastructure providers, CADRE presents a robust, scalable solution for sensitive data governance in Australia. The platform's deployment represents a significant advancement in the Australian research community's ability to securely access and share data. As CADRE moves toward widespread adoption, it has the

potential to transform how sensitive data is managed, accessed, and used in research across Australia and internationally.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

Project plan aims

The CADRE project is aimed at filling a gap that currently exists in national research infrastructure that is, there is no existing integrated infrastructure that enables high volumes of social science researchers and related disciplines to *efficiently and safely* secure access to sensitive data maintained in higher education and government agencies.

- The CADRE platform developed will align the secure access procedures and technologies required to store and analyse data.
- The CADRE partners, community members and key stakeholders will ensure that researcher and secure access requirements guide platform design and drive uptake of the platform.

Achievement of project aims

The CADRE project successfully met its primary aims through the completion of five sequential project deliverables. These deliverables addressed the identified gaps in national research infrastructure by developing and delivering a shared and distributed platform to enable secure and efficient access to sensitive data for the social sciences and related disciplines. Below is a summary of how each deliverable contributed to the achievement of project aims.

a) Development of framework and protocols

The first critical step in achieving CADRE's objectives was the collaborative development of a shared conceptual framework. Representatives from multiple project partners worked together to align the platform's design with the principles of the Five Safes framework, ensuring secure and ethical data access and governance. This foundational work resulted in the publication of a conceptual framework document ([10.5281/zenodo.5748610](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5748610)) providing the basis for the CADRE platform's development.

Simultaneously, a technical working group was convened to develop detailed information exchange protocols. These protocols defined the accreditation and identification data to be exchanged between data users, providers, and service facilities within the CADRE ecosystem. Key outputs include an unpublished report, *Analysis of the Required Functions of CADRE Services*, and a solutions architecture report (available as final project report supplementary material). These deliverables laid the groundwork for the platform's technical functionality.

b) Deploy and run an integrated data access management platform

The CADRE platform development progressed steadily through iterative testing and refinement. The initial product development phase was completed in April 2024, resulting in a fully functional platform ready for testing. End to end testing was conducted first by ADA staff, and later by ARDC (Australian Research Data Commons) users, confirming that the platform met the requirements for integrating

independent data service providers and completing full request to access workflows. The production environment was finalised and comprehensively tested in September 2024.

Deployment to production is scheduled for January 20, 2025. This timeline was strategically chosen to ensure the availability of technical support staff. The Chief Investigator has confirmed that the production version is functionally identical to the tested instance, with no known concerns for the January 2025 launch.

c) Integration of data service providers

To date, four service providers have been successfully integrated into the CADRE platform, with an additional use case, the Melbourne Institute Data Lab (MIDL) integration detailed below, piloted earlier in the development of the platform. Successful integration is defined as the ability for data providers to manage data requests end-to-end through CADRE, including authentication, workflow execution, and generation of data sharing agreements. These integrations demonstrate CADRE's capability to accommodate diverse data services and workflows:

- **Australian Data Archive (ADA):** Integration of the Dataverse catalogue, archival workflow processes, and access management systems. Use of CADRE/CoManage Groups and corresponding Dataverse Dataset Groups with members of these groups being those who have been approved to access the actual data. This end-to-end integration has been shown to work with `dataverse-test.ada.edu.au <-> stage.cadre.ada.edu.au`.

Once CADRE is deployed into production, a subset of datasets/collections from ADA's `dataverse.ada.edu.au` instance will be selected to be made requestable through CADRE. This requires setting up the components in CADRE and deploying already implemented javascript to `dataverse.ada.edu.au` to tie the two platforms together. The ADA developer will programmatically set up the CADRE components for the selected subset of datasets – this will take a few hours at most; the ADA devops will deploy the javascript to Dataverse. This will be completed in January/February 2025, in line with the launch of CADRE.

- **Language Data Commons of Australia (LDA CA):** Integration of the LDA CA data portal, CILogon authentication service, and license-request workflows. The LDA CA team has thoroughly tested (11/12/2024) the integration of their licence workflow in CADRE and confirmed that the integration can proceed. The CADRE team has established administrative access to LDA CA for testing and creation of CADRE assets. LDA CA and the CADRE teams are currently working with CILogon to enable additional capabilities required by LDA CA. Full deployment of the LDA CA intergration is expected by February 2025.
- **Social Data Analytics (SoDA) Lab:** External SoDA Lab service hosts data – facilitating access to that data will be managed by SoDA Lab. SoDA Lab to set up resources for requesting access to that data in CADRE and manage the Data Sharing Request approvals. CADRE has met with the SoDA Lab representatives to guide them on setting up each component. The timing of the SoDA Lab's integration is dependent on the SoDA Lab's resource availability and priority roadmap. The

goal for this integration to be completed is Q1 2025.

- **RLA Health and Wellbeing Co-Op:** Data to be deposited into the ADA Dataverse catalogue as datasets; corresponding resources will be created in CADRE for requesting access to those datasets. The RLA team is currently (11/12/2024) in the process of data curation for deposit into ADA's catalogue. The ADA integration described above will apply to the second part of the RLA integration. CADRE has met with Co-Op representatives to guide them on setting up each component. Representatives for both SoDA Lab and RLA Co-op have confirmed that CADRE's access management workflows are suitable, and full integration is expected in early 2025 pending approval from all data custodians associated with those organisations.
- **Melbourne Institute Data Lab (MIDL):** MIDL will add users who complete a specific subset of MIDL courses to CADRE via API. MIDL will also deposit a subset of newly created datasets as outputs from MIDL into the ADA Dataverse catalogues as datasets and corresponding resources will be created in CADRE for requesting access to those datasets. The MIDL training via CADRE update was shown to work as a proof of concept. The MIDL team was also able to create new datasets in a testing Dataverse installation and set up corresponding resources in CADRE for users to request access to those datasets. It is anticipated that MIDL will follow this same process for CADRE in production. The CADRE team worked closely with MIDL to guide them on using the CADRE API and on setting up each component. A MIDL integration with CADRE in production is dependent on MIDL's roadmap and their continued priority in pursuing this integration. CADRE anticipates integration could be completed by the end of Q1 2025.

Each integration showcases CADRE's adaptability and interoperability, ensuring the platform's relevance across various research data collections and organisational workflows.

Adaptations to Integration Plans

The CADRE project successfully addressed integration challenges by prioritizing collaboration with AAF, CILogon, and newly identified service providers. This approach enabled key substitute integrations, such as replacing AREN and AARNet Sensitive Data with MIDL, engaging LDaCA as a late-stage partner, and adjusting integration plans for SoDA Lab. While some originally planned integrations, such as AARNet's secure environment and harvesting functions for AURIN and Research Graph, were not completed, the project achieved a sufficient array of integrations to meet immediate platform needs and demonstrate capability for future expansion.

d) Training of platform users and engagement with the research community

Effective training and community engagement have been central to ensuring the CADRE platform's usability and provide a strong framework for continued adoption. The platform itself includes functionality for hosting and sharing training resources that can be assigned as conditional for data access. Key engagement activities have included demonstrations, webinars, and workshops (see section 2.3), which have been instrumental in familiarising the research community with CADRE's features and benefits.

2. DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1. Achievements against project work packages/deliverables:

Link to November 2024 traffic light status report:

[CADRE Traffic light status report](#)

2.2. Project outputs and outcomes

2.2.1 Outputs

OUTPUTS	RESULTS SUMMARY	EVIDENCE
Web-based data access management platform	The platform is complete and scheduled for release on 20 th January 2025.	<p>The CADRE platform has been developed and is ready for deployment on 20 January 2025 at cadre.ada.edu.au</p> <p>The application was tested and the core functionality was confirmed by ARDC, including the ADA Dataverse integration (10/12/2024). ADA has provided documentation confirming the steps required to migrate CADRE from stage to production prior to deployment.</p>
Shared conceptual framework report	<p>Published on Zenodo.</p> <p>1152 views 639 downloads</p>	<p>CADRE Five Safes Framework – Conceptualisation and Operationalisation of the Five Safes Framework</p> <p>10.5281/zenodo.5748610</p>
Information exchange protocol reports	The information exchange protocols were developed with members of the Technical Working Group (TWG).	<p>CADRE Information Exchange - Presentation at IASSIST 2022</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/records/6630335</p> <p>CADRE Required Functions Report</p>

OUTPUTS	RESULTS SUMMARY	EVIDENCE
		<p><i>[Final report supplementary material]</i></p> <p>CADRE Solutions Architecture Report</p> <p><i>[Final report supplementary material]</i></p>
<p>Reports on implications for qualitative data</p>	<p>Deliverables from project partner The University of Melbourne included two reports exploring the implications of the CADRE platform for qualitative data.</p>	<p>Governance of qualitative data sharing in Australia</p> <p>29 May 2024, <i>Analysis & Policy Observatory</i> DOI: 10.60836/x51y-g630 https://apo.org.au/node/328064</p> <p>Archiving and sharing qualitative data: implications for data management platforms</p> <p>29 May 2024, <i>Analysis & Policy Observatory</i> DOI: 10.60836/pqbc-jw49 https://apo.org.au/node/328065</p>
<p>Training and engagement materials</p>	<p>A wide range of original training and engagement materials were produced for CADRE including Moodle training courses that are integrated with the CADRE platform; introductory videos available on YouTube; and numerous workshops, seminars, and conference presentations.</p>	<p>See section 2.3 in this report for links to training and engagement materials where available.</p>

2.2.2 Outcomes

OUTCOME	RESULTS SUMMARY	EVIDENCE
<p><i>NB. Outcomes from the project plan are also recorded as WP</i></p>		

OUTCOME	RESULTS SUMMARY	EVIDENCE
<i>milestones/deliverables in the traffic light report.</i>		
Shared conceptual framework	Efficiently and reliably connecting the elements of the Five Safes – People, Projects, Data, Settings and Outputs	CADRE Five Safes Framework – Conceptualisation and Operationalisation of the Five Safes Framework 10.5281/zenodo.5748610
Information exchange protocols	Exchanging identifier and accreditation information between data users, providers and trusted access facilities – based on the AAF identity provision model	CADRE Information Exchange - Presentation at IASSIST 2022 https://zenodo.org/records/6630335 CADRE Required Functions Report <i>[Final report supplementary material]</i> CADRE Solutions Architecture Report <i>[Final report supplementary material]</i>
Integrated data access management platform	Managing data access requests from researchers and data supply from providers	The CADRE platform has been developed and is ready for deployment on 20 January 2025 at cadre.ada.edu.au The application was tested and the core functionality was confirmed by ARDC, including the ADA Dataverse integration (10/12/2024). ADA has provided documentation confirming the steps required to migrate CADRE from stage to production prior to deployment.

OUTCOME	RESULTS SUMMARY	EVIDENCE
Pilot and production platform integrations	<p>Ensuring the four secure data access settings can interoperate:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data Co-Ops (SoDA, SWIN) 2. AURIN (AURIN) 3. MIDL (University of Melbourne) 4. ADA (ANU) <p>Exploring pilot integrations with project affiliates e.g., via ERICA project (UNSW & AIHW)</p>	<p>The application was tested and the core functionality was confirmed by ARDC, including the ADA Dataverse integration (10/12/2024).</p> <p>Due to changes at partner organisations, replacement integrations were negotiated with ARDC during the life of the project. As detailed in section 1.2 of this report, these additional integrations have been successfully piloted and/or confirmed by platform owners as going ahead.</p>

2.3. Outreach and training activities

ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS	DATE OF ACTIVITY
Webinar	<p>Coordinated Access for Data, Researchers and Environments (CADRE)</p> <p>https://www.eventbrite.com.au/e/coordinated-access-for-data-researchers-and-environments-cadre-tickets-1029708033447</p> <p>https://ardc.edu.au/event/coordinated-access-for-data-researchers-and-environments-cadre-a-showcase/</p>	50 registered	12/12/2024
Stall	<p>ANU Research Infrastructure Expo</p> <p>https://www.anu.edu.au/anu-research-infrastructure-expo-2024</p>	NA	28/11/2024

Workshop	<p>ResBaz QLD 2024</p> <p>A New Tool for Managing Access to Sensitive Research Data</p> <p>https://resbaz.github.io/resbaz2024qld/schedule/#session-2006</p>	18 registered	06/11/2024
Training Materials	<p>Training Materials for Five Safes Framework – self-completed online</p> <p>DRESA</p> <p>Zenodo</p>	<p>Zenodo Metrics:</p> <p>105 views</p> <p>35 downloads</p>	21/12/2023
Stall	<p>ANU Research Infrastructure Expo</p> <p>https://services.anu.edu.au/news-events/2023-anu-research-infrastructure-expo</p>	NA	28/11/2023
Stall	<p>eResearch</p> <p>https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/2023-conference/</p>	NA	17-19/10/2023
BoF	<p>eResearch</p> <p>“How Training Development through Collaboration, can Support Organisational Strategies for Safe Data Management”</p> <p>https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/2023-conference/2023-program/</p>	10	17/10/2023
Moodle Online	1. Module 1: Fives Safes for	30	01/08/2023

<p>Training Modules</p>	<p>Sensitive Data Management</p> <p>2. Module 2: Roles and Responsibilities</p> <p>https://learning.cadre5safes.org.au/</p>		
<p>Roundtable</p>	<p>Implementing Indigenous Data Licensing and Access</p> <p>https://ardc.edu.au/article/implementing-indigenous-data-licensing-and-access/</p>	<p>32</p>	<p>03-05/07/2023</p>
<p>Workshop</p>	<p>UNSW + CADRE Five Safes, Sensitive Data Workshop</p>	<p>25 registered</p>	<p>09/05/2023</p>
<p>Stall</p>	<p>Volunteering Australia Conference</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>14/02/2023</p>

Presentation	<p>Data + Five Safes</p> <p>https://ardc.edu.au/event/has-s-rdc-and-irc-computational-skills-summer-school/</p>	~30	07/02/2023
Stall	<p>ResBaz QLD 2022</p>	NA	02-03/11/2022
Presentation	<p>ResBaz QLD 2022</p> <p>“Introduction to the Fives Sages for Sensitive Data”</p> <p>https://resbaz.github.io/resbaz2022qld/schedule/</p>	15	02/11/2022
Stall	<p>eResearch 2022</p>	NA	18/10/2022 – 20 Oct 2022

Paid Workshop	<p>eResearch</p> <p>“Learn about the Five Safes Framework – a guide to enabling researcher access to sensitive data”</p> <p>https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/2022-conference/2022-program/</p>	15	17 Oct
Stall	<p>eResearch 2022</p> <p>https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/2022-conference/2022-program/</p>	NA	18/10/2022 – 20 Oct 2022
Presentation	<p>eResearch 2022</p> <p>“Sensitive Data Management: authorisation decision support”</p> <p>https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/2022-conference/2022-program/#tuesday</p>	Unknown	19/10/2022
BoF	<p>eResearch 2022</p> <p>“Pathfinder for a Trust</p>	Unknown	19/10/2022

	and Identity Framework and Infrastructure for NCRIS”		
Workshop	CADRE Five Safes Pilot Workshops University of Melbourne Online ANU	22	29/09/2022 05/10/2022 11/10/2022
Presentation	“CADRE Conceptual Framework – a model for the management of sensitive data and the Five Safes” https://youtu.be/F6BX2pD1H0s?si=xtBUlycTxGJbmouG	Youtube views: 106	15/09/2022
YouTube Videos	Explainer video of Sensitive Data: https://youtu.be/RmNLksknc5A?si=pJN7sYAVFZc7GUpY Five Safes: https://youtu.be/VeHDtSGEaJQ?si=uUKD7ideqdNVMZeQ Intro to CADRE: https://youtu.be/BbT_3qyeDM0?si=tA0Zg9MyjWWCwaWe	Total views: 179	2022 - 2023
Presentation	IASSIST 2022 “CADRE Five Safes Framework”	Unknown	10/06/2022

	https://zenodo.org/records/6630417		
Presentation	<p>IASSIST 2022 “CADRE Platform Information Exchange”</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/records/6630335</p>	Unknown	10/06/2022
Presentation	<p>eResearch New Zealand 2022 “Looking through the Five Safes Lens – Sensitive Data Sharing Agreements and Research Workflows”</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/records/10129675</p>	Unknown	09/02/2022
Presentation	<p>eResearch 2021</p> <p>“Sensitive Data and Information standards – shared territory with rich rewards”</p> <p>https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/eresearch-australasia-conference-2021/2021-program/</p>	Unknown	14/10/2021
BoF	<p>eResearch 2021</p> <p>“The Current State and Future Potential of Australian Research Platforms – CADRE Five Safes Framework (lightning talk)”</p> <p>https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/eresearch-australasia-</p>	Unknown	11/10/2021

	conference-2021/2021-program/		
Presentation	<p>IFLA WLIC 2021 Conference</p> <p>“Diversifying Collaboration: Network Complexity and Big Data”</p> <p>https://www.ifla.org/events/wlic-2021-virtual-conference-open-programme-by-the-acquisition-and-collection-development-section/</p> <p>Slides:</p> <p>https://cadre5safes.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/IFLA_WLIC2021_Mason.pdf</p>	Unknown	19/08/2021

3. PROJECT IMPACT

3.1. Impact stories

Note that user stories are not available as the platform launch is scheduled for January 2025. Although the platform has not yet launched, CADRE is expected to streamline sensitive data access for researchers and enhance governance for data providers. By reducing administrative overhead and ensuring compliance, CADRE will enable more efficient and secure collaboration across institutions and support the reuse and utilisation of valuable research data.

Impact stories:

1. CADRE is the first Australian entity to adopt the Authentication and Authorisation for Research Collaborations (AARC) framework. The implementation of this policy framework was adapted from the AAF NRI Policy Development Toolkit. The framework is widely used internationally, including

by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC-Life), Large Hadron Collider (LHC), and the National Institutes of Health (NIH). The AARC policy framework establishes a shared sense of trust for users, providers, and administrators across distributed research services. On the basis of this work, the Australian Data Archive is in the process of updating their terms of use to more closely reflect the AARC framework.

2. The integration of the Language Data Commons of Australia (LDaCA) with CADRE has led to shared use of the CILogon authentication service. Providing access to CILogon through a shared subscription model is a valuable component of the CADRE infrastructure that is made available to data service providers and custodians in Australia.
3. Dialogue with representatives from the Office of the National Data Commissioner around the DataPlace platform development covered the research requirements that are coordinated by the CADRE project. The CADRE project captures common processes for access to sensitive data, ethics oversight and researcher training in higher education that informed the DataPlace development.
4. CADRE Community Coordinator was invited to participate in the ARDC SeRP Project Research Users Community of Practice. The COP was developing Five Safes training for their platform users which CADRE had already completed. This resulted in a presentation at eResearch 2023 where it featured CADRE, Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation (QCIF) and Monash University.
5. Engagement with the QCIF KeyPoint team resulted in meetings and presentations. CADRE project team met with senior members of the QCIF KeyPoint team. These meetings were to discuss the developments of both platforms and how to address challenges of managing access to sensitive data. The CADRE Community Coordinator was able to attend their online Five Safes training and provide feedback. CADRE Moodle training was shared for feedback from QCIF. The projects partnered on two presentations, one at QLD ResBaz 2022 and as previously mentioned, eResearch 2023.

3.2. Impact metrics

3.2.1. Use, Outreach and Communications Metrics

ARDC realises that a number of possible impact metrics are lag indicators.

IMPACT METRIC	PROJECT TOTAL TO DATE	DESCRIPTION, LINKS and DOIs
Number of publications citing project or project outputs	14	See table 3.2.2 for details.
Current number of users	Metric to be evaluated post-deployment	Number of platform users will be available after deployment on 20 January 2025.

Number of active users (over 90-day period)	Metric to be evaluated post-deployment	Active use of the platform will only be available after deployment on 20 January 2025.
Number of jobs run (i.e. number of processes submitted)	Metric to be evaluated post-deployment	The number of data requests submitted and approved via the platform will only be available after deployment on 20 January 2025.
Availability of the infrastructure (days in operation vs days offline)	Metric to be evaluated post-deployment	The platform will only become available after deployment on 20 January 2025.
Number of outreach activities (e.g. seminars, presentations)	28	Included – presentations, webinars, stalls at various conferences, training See table 2.1 for more details.
Number of researchers trained (online or face-to-face)	52	3 x Workshops to introduce CADRE as well as test some content in develop for the Moodle Modules Moodle Online Modules (see entry in table 2.1 for more details)
Social media mentions	20	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7261050223702011904/</p> <p>The screenshot shows a LinkedIn post by Shokoufeh Ghalibafan, a PhD student at QUT. The post describes her experience at the Research Bazaar (ResBaz QLD) at ACU in Brisbane, highlighting workshops on CADRE, data cleaning, and R Shiny, as well as networking opportunities.</p>

		<p>https://x.com/kyliesadler79/status/1587636024477306881</p> <p>https://x.com/SOCEY2/status/1585830170941829121</p> <p>https://x.com/stevenmce/status/158088118773252096</p> <p>https://x.com/digitalstudioUM/status/1570639292304850944</p> <p>https://x.com/ARDC_AU/status/1570156871301971968</p> <p>https://x.com/ARDC_AU/status/1569143888492875776</p> <p>https://x.com/ARDC_AU/status/1567331962620203008</p> <p>https://x.com/amir_aryani/status/1566747346876366848</p> <p>https://x.com/SOCEY2/status/1565558719966244864</p> <p>https://x.com/1n9r1d/status/1560542931437506560</p> <p>https://x.com/SOCEY2/status/1559045031549599744</p> <p>https://x.com/ragamouf/status/1524215612096258049</p>
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<p>Blog posts/news articles that reference infrastructure or service</p>	<p>15</p>	<p>ARDC: https://ardc.edu.au/article/our-platforms-investment/</p> <p>https://ardc.edu.au/project/cadre/</p> <p>UNSW: https://www.unsw.edu.au/research/cbdrh/our-research/our-projects/coordinated-access-for-data-researchers-and-environments</p> <p>CADRE Blog: https://cadre5safes.org.au/</p> <p>SOCEY: https://www.socey.net/2021/11/27/cadre/</p>

		https://mailchi.mp/8d7ba6e14dbd/latest-news-first-socey-newsletter-15886353
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3.2.2. Links to Publications and Other Communications

Publications that cite/reference the platform/infrastructure

DATE	CITATION WITH DOI
29/05/2024	McLeod, O'Connor & Davis (2024, May 29). Governance of qualitative data sharing in Australia. Analysis & Policy Observatory. https://doi.org/10.60836/x51y-g630
29/05/2024	McLeod, O'Connor & Davis (2024, May 29). Archiving and sharing qualitative data: Implications for data management platforms. Analysis & Policy Observatory. https://doi.org/10.60836/pqbc-jw49
18/03/2024	Ritchie, F., & Whittard, D. (2024). Using the Five Safes to structure economic evaluations of data governance. <i>Data & Policy</i> , 6, e16. https://doi.org/10.1017/dap.2024.12
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Social media mentions of the platform/infrastructure

DATE	LINK
	See table 2.1.1

Blog posts/news articles that reference the platform/infrastructure

DATE	LINK
	See table 2.1.1